

Title: The role of the Immune system in Alzheimer's Disease

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Abstract

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a neurodegenerative disease and the most common form of dementia. AD is a progressive disorder that presents multiple different symptoms. Early symptoms can include the loss of memory and mild cognitive ability, however, later symptoms can present with increased severity and lack of motor/body control. There is currently no cure for AD and current treatment regimens can only temporally ease symptoms or slow progression. Although multiple clinical trials are progressing to develop antibody-based treatments targeting Amyloid Beta ($A\beta$), one of the hallmark biomarkers of AD onset, these have shown no more than minimal effect. AD is one of the leading causes of death in the UK and with an ever-increasing ageing society is predicted to only increase in numbers posing a significant global emergency. AD is a complex pathophysiological disorder that is driven by a combination of both genetic and immunological processes in disease development. It is widely accepted that immune cells of both the innate and adaptive arm are found within the central nervous system and data now indicates that these cells can also be found in the brain residing in the brain parenchyma [1]. The role that these cells play in AD progression will be discussed in this review.

Keywords

Alzheimer's Disease, Immune system, Neuroinflammation, Immunotherapy

Introduction

Dementia is currently the leading cause of death in women and the second in men in the UK [2] and also represents a significant global health burden. Late onset AD is most the common form of dementia which results in a group of related symptoms that are associated with decline of brain function which progresses into more complicated and severe conditions. Early symptoms include loss of memory, language, visuospatial awareness, concentration, orientation and mood. Late symptoms include delusions, hallucinations, personality loss, and lack of body/motor control. There are currently 850,000 people suffering in the U.K with dementia which is expected to continue to rise [3]. This devastating impact on human life is further exacerbated by the lack of any effective treatment and poses a significant financial burden to the NHS, commanding £26 billion of the NHS annual budget [3]. AD pathology is driven by a combination of genetic, environmental and key immunological processes that can exacerbate one another in a vicious cycle driving disease development. It is widely accepted that both innate and adaptive immune cells are found within the central nervous system (CNS) in multiple neuropathological disorders and the role of the immune system contributing and exacerbating AD pathology is not a new phenomenon and has been studied extensively for years. However, recent interest in neuroimmunology has refocused research attention to study key immunological mechanisms that contribute to AD pathology. This review discusses

some of these recent findings and delineates the relationship between homeostatic immune control and dysregulated immune responses with AD.

AD Pathology

AD is typically clinically classified by the accumulation of Amyloid Beta ($A\beta$) plaques and hyper-phosphorylated tau protein which gives rise to the presence of Neurofibrillary tangles (NFTs). This then leads to brain synapse damage and the loss of function of homeostatic properties of the brain, including the function of neuronal cells and efficient blood brain barrier (BBB) protection [4, 5]. The $A\beta$ peptide originates from amyloid precursor protein (APP) peptide that is proteolytically cleaved by either an alpha-, beta- or gamma-secretase resulting in the production of varying length peptides (37–43 amino acids) [6]. Typically, $A\beta_{40}$ and $A\beta_{42}$ are the most abundant forms with $A\beta_{40}$ mostly abundant in non-pathological conditions [7, 8]. Excessive overproduction of $A\beta_{42}$ peptide, genetic mutations or longer isoforms of $A\beta$ increases $A\beta$ aggregate formation. Aggregates of $A\beta_{42}$ can form oligomers and accumulate in the parenchyma. These amyloid plaques are then associated with a recruitment of microglia and astrocytes and inflammation of the axons and dendrites [8].

Tau is a microtubule-associated axon enriched protein that becomes hyperphosphorylated in AD forming prion like structures that spread throughout the parenchyma which can become activated via post translational modifications and initiates tau-specific neuropathology and NFT formation through destabilisation of neuronal microtubules [4]. $A\beta$ is upstream of tau in AD pathogenesis and can trigger the conversion of tau into a toxic state. Tau is also required for $A\beta$ toxicity *in vivo* and $A\beta$ initiates a pathway leading to tau-dependant synaptic dysfunction that directly correlates with the symptoms of progressive cognitive decline in patients [4]. The combination of the increase of $A\beta$ and tau proteins with subsequent plaque formation and tangle development gives rise to the progressive symptoms of AD [4]. Understanding the relationship between $A\beta$, tau and the immune system may help identify novel ways to treat AD.

Genetic risk factors in AD

Genetic risk factors of AD can be classified and subtyped based on the patients age of disease onset and the method of inheritance. In genetic terms these are classified as Early Onset AD (EOAD), and Late Onset AD (LOAD). EOAD is commonly referred to as Familial AD and the individual receives one allele from either parent in an autosomal dominant pattern that is sufficient to cause disease [9]. EOAD is a rare form of AD and is caused by mutations in either Amyloid Precursor Protein (APP), presenilin1 (PSEN1) or presenilin 2 (PSEN2) that develops between the ages of 30-60 [8]. LOAD, also referred to as Sporadic AD, is more polygenic and presents after the age of 65. Multiple risk factors including age, environmental factors and multiple genetic variants can associate with LOAD [9].

Studies using large-scale genome wide associated approaches (GWAS) and whole genome analyses have identified many immune-specific genes associated with AD pathology. These include importantly *APOE*, *TREM2*, *CD33*, *CLU*, *CR1*, *PLCG2*, *ABI3* and the *MS4A* and *HLA* families [8, 10] among others and their association of immune functions with AD are well described by Frost *et al* [10]. The 28 risk loci genes described by Frost *et al* highlight the significant contribution of immune related genes and risk of subsequent AD pathology.

The *APOE* gene encodes apolipoprotein E and was the first genetic risk factor found associated with LOAD and is the most highly linked risk loci to AD. *APOE* regulates lipid transport and is homeostatically expressed by astrocytes and oligodendrocytes but expression

of APOE is greatly increased by reactive microglia during AD [8]. Microglia are one of the key resident immune resident cells in the brain and CNS and act as first responders to inflammatory activators [11]. APOE has been shown to regulate A β levels in an APOE-isoform-dependent manner [5] with individuals carrying the ϵ 4 allelic isoform of the gene (*APO ϵ 4*) encoding APOE4, having a three-to-four-fold increase in the likelihood of developing AD [5, 12] with concurrent increased A β aggregates [13] whereas the ϵ 2 allelic isoform (*APO ϵ 2*) enhances A β clearance and carriers of this isoform have lower AD risk [14].

APOE is also important in tau regulation and tauopathy development with a similar allelic isoform risk to A β formation. APOE4 can lead to increased neurodegeneration with increased tau levels in humans [15] while mouse studies have shown that APOE4 results in higher tau pathology and an increase in reactive microglia and astrocytes as compared to APOE2 or APOE3 [15, 16]. APOE4 can also lead to BBB dysfunction, even in cognitively intact individuals, but can result in more severe BBB dysfunction in cognitively impaired individuals even though no effect on cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) A β and tau levels are observed [17, 18].

Interestingly the APOE2, 3 and 4 isoforms have been shown to bind with high affinity to the protein product of another AD risk factor loci *TREM2*, promoting phagocytosis of *neurons in vitro*. *TREM2* which is a microglial transmembrane receptor that promotes phagocytosis, cell survival and cytokine release [19-21]. *TREM2* is proteolytically processed by ADAM10 and releases soluble *TREM2* (s*TREM2*) into the CSF [22, 23] with levels peaking following A β deposition and correlates with the onset of AD symptoms [22]. The phagocytic response initiated after *TREM2* activation is also associated with increases in cytokine production including TGF- β and IL-1 [24-26]. Mouse studies have shown the importance of *TREM2* in AD where *Trem2*^{-/-} AD mice (heterozygous for R47H), showed increased microglial apoptosis with a concurrent decrease in A β clearance [27]. The significance of *TREM2* and thus effective microglial function was supported by a study showing an overexpression of *TREM2* improved cognition and promoted microglia to ameliorate inflammatory release [28]. This is further supported by *TREM2* variant alleles such as R47H, which is believed to result in loss of microglial function and increases the risk of developing AD by 2- to 4-fold [29]. More recent studies have now focussed on targeting *TREM2* directly using monoclonal antibodies and have shown efficacy in reducing cognitive function and microglial activation using 5xFAD AD mice [30, 31]. These studies further showed that engineered antibodies could bind both human and murine *TREM2* and in humans was capable of binding soluble *TREM2* in the CSF of AD patients [30, 31]. These molecules show therapeutic potential and can cross the BBB when systemically administered [31]. Further studies have utilised chaperone transport molecules to transport anti-*TREM2* activating antibodies across the BBB that increases microglial activation and metabolism [32]. Whilst these studies show promise and highlights *TREM2* as an exciting therapeutic target, it requires much more detailed examination.

In summary these highlights the importance of linking genetic to functional studies and emphasises the significance that both APOE and *TREM2* have on AD development and the importance of microglial activity in protective AD control.

APOE and *TREM2* possess an intrinsic link that enables them to communicate with other key immune modulators, including *CD33*, another high-risk loci for AD development, and is expressed on both microglia and infiltrating macrophages but can coordinate their expression giving rise to opposing functions [33]. *CD33* signalling inhibits cellular activity such as phagocytosis by promoting phosphorylation of immunoreceptor tyrosine-based inhibitor motifs and subsequent suppression of inflammatory responses. Risk allele variants in patients with AD show increased expression of *CD33* with concurrent decreases in A β clearance. Whilst studies have shown increased expression of *CD33* in the periphery and the brain of AD patients [34], genetic deletion of *CD33* in macrophages and microglia *in vitro* increased A β 41-42 phagocytosis but increased oxidative burst and inflammation [35]. Molecules that target

APOE, TREM2 and CD33 as described here show encouraging efficacy but requires further study.

The immune system and AD

The brain was classically thought to be a site of immune privilege that was inaccessible to the systemic immune system. However, multiple studies have revealed a direct link between the brain and circulating immune cells, exposing new immunological processes that may directly contribute to AD pathology [36-38]. Neuroinflammation is observed and well characterised in AD patients and mouse models of AD with most studies focussing on the regulative properties of microglia as a source of inflammation. This direct brain/systemic immune system interaction, combined with BBB dysregulation, permits the recruitment of innate and adaptive immune cells into the brain. The neuroinflammatory contributions of the immune system that drive AD pathology have been well described over recent years and will be discussed below.

Innate Immunity

The association between immune cell function and genetic risk loci has been well classified, with the complement system identified as a key regulator of AD development. The complement system consists of three main activatory pathways, either classical, alternative or lectin pathways [39]. These pathways are activated after recognition of different target proteins, antigens or bacteria. Microglia, astrocytes and neurons in the brain express most complement receptors and secrete more complement proteins than any other brain-resident cell [40].

There is substantial evidence that the complement pathway is significantly upregulated in AD. The initiating protein of the classical complement pathway, C1q (classical), has been shown to be activated *in vivo* by A β peptide in AD patients and shown to cause neuronal atrophy [41]. Further in AD mice, C1q is elevated prior to any plaque formation suggesting C1q activation is an early trigger of disease. C1q can also bind to A β and APOE directly where C1q-APOE complexes have been found both in the choroid plexus and A β plaques in AD patients and in APP/PS1-21 AD mice [19, 42]

The C3 complement protein is also able to regulate AD development [43]. C3 is downstream of C1q and mouse studies that inhibit either C1q, C3 or CR3 (microglial complement receptor) or that use *C3ar*^{-/-} animals can decrease synapse loss [44] and attenuate neuroinflammation, tau pathology and synaptic defects [43, 45].

However, studies have shown that in aged transgenic mice, the absence of C3 protects against synapse loss and cognitive decline even in the presence of A β plaques [46] which suggests that A β plaque formation may be regulated by C3. An increase in C3 production is also associated with an increase in NF- κ B-mediated inflammation. NF- κ B is a transcription factor and has been shown to be elevated in the brains of AD patients [47, 48]. *In vivo* studies have shown that NF- κ B activation elevates astrocyte derived C3 as compared to *Nf- κ B*^{-/-} mice that display decreased levels of synapse formations [43]. The importance of C3 in AD development is further supported by the presence of C3 protein in AD patients' brains and in APP/PS1-21 AD mice there is an increase in C3 mRNA levels. These data show complement to be a driving force of AD pathology, particularly A β pathology and tau mediated neurodegeneration. It therefore presents the complement pathway proteins, particularly those that converge at the C3 protein, as a significant targets for therapeutic intervention. Studies targeting other complement pathway proteins have shown efficacy in improving AD pathology where siRNA silencing of C5 attenuates A β -mediated microglial accumulation [8, 42].

There have been multiple studies showing that inflammation induced by the innate immune system contributes to AD development. This inflammation can be caused through systemic or localised cellular activation or dysregulation after brain impact (concussion or traumatic injury), autoimmunity, obesity, and environmental factors such as cigarette smoke. The innate immune response is a typically very rapid response and initiates within minutes. Here pattern recognition receptors (PRRs) and danger associated molecular patterns (DAMPs) expressed by host cells recognise invading pathogens and molecular patterns via Toll-like receptors (TLRs). Activating TLRs through polyriboinosinic-polyribocytidylic acid (polyI:C) stimulation (TLR3 agonist) has been shown to stimulate AD-like neuropathology in aged wild-type mice with concurrent elevation of APP in the hippocampus with altered tau phosphorylation [49]. As described above NF- κ B plays a critical role in AD development and activation of TLRs in innate immune cells are essential for stimulating NF- κ B activation and subsequent inflammation via proinflammatory cytokine release [50]. TLR activation can also result in the activation of the nucleotide-binding domain leucine-rich repeat and pyrin domain containing receptor protein 3 (NLRP3), a key inflammasome scaffold molecule and PRR [51]. NLRP3 is also expressed on microglia and upon activation stimulates the release of proinflammatory cytokines IL-1 β , IL-18 and caspase-1. *Nlrp3*^{-/-} and *Caspase-1*^{-/-} mice have reduced A β plaque formation and increased A β microglial phagocytosis and reduced IL-1 β release is seen in APP/PS1-21 AD mice [52] suggesting that the inflammasome is an important immune mediator of innate pro-inflammatory cytokine release in AD pathology.

The exposure of the brain parenchyma to the full force of the immune system can be further exacerbated through loss of homeostatic protective measures, including BBB damage or dysregulation, systemic and vascular inflammation or impaired meningeal lymphatic drainage, all of which are observed in AD [8]. This will subsequently lead to infiltration and recruitment of systemic immune cells into the brain contributing, in the context of AD, to neuroinflammation and AD pathology. Neutrophils are one of the first blood borne innate immune cells that can respond to inflammation and are found in the CNS and brain parenchyma of 5xFAD and 3xTG AD mice [53, 54]. This is mediated by LFA-1 release and results in neutrophils surrounding the A β plaques. Direct targeting of LFA-1 using systemic administration of anti-LFA1 blocking antibodies can reduce neutrophil recruitment and leakage and also reduces amyloid plaques and cognitive decline [53].

Interestingly A β has been shown to display anti-microbial properties [55] and that synthetic A β peptide treatment exhibits potent *in vitro* antimicrobial activity towards eight common and clinically relevant microbial pathogens [56]. This was later supported *in vivo* using 5xFAD AD mice, showing A β helped protect against *Caenorhabditis elegans* infection and that mice lacking APP have decreased survival post bacterial infection [57]. The authors described how amyloid oligomerisation mediates the protective capacity of A β and the presence of microbial cells within the cerebrum accelerates A β deposition in 5xFAD AD mice [57]. The antimicrobial role of A β has been supported by studies where A β 42-overexpressing cells are shown to be resistant to killing by yeast and bacteria [58]. This presents an important finding in AD development. If as suggested by Frost *et al* that APP and A β is involved in pathogen defence, then excessive A β production could be a by-product from innate immune cell activation supporting the hypothesis that infectious pathogens could play a vital role in AD development [10].

Adaptive Immunity

One of the most described adaptive immune cells that contribute to AD pathology are T cells [18]. Multiple studies in both humans and mice have shown the presence of T cells in the post-mortem human brain during AD including the leptomeninges and the hippocampus, with mouse studies describing a concurrent increased prevalence of T cells, A β and tau (reviewed in [18]). This is further supported by data showing that increased T cell accumulation (more

CD8⁺ than CD4⁺ T cells) in the hippocampus is associated with more severe human AD [18, 59, 60]. However, some studies have described how an increase in CD8⁺ T cells correlates with increased tau but not A β formation [60] and may potentially be linked to overall systemic inflammaging (chronic inflammation when ageing) [61] where an influx of inflammatory T cells into the brain correlates to an aged individual.

However, there is conflicting evidence as to the role of T and B cells in AD pathology. Crossing *Rag2*^{-/-} and *Il2r γ* ^{-/-} mice with 5xFAD mice generates an AD mouse model system deficient of T, B and Natural Killer (NK) cells that results in an increase in severe A β pathology with enhanced neuroinflammation and decreased microglial activation [62]. Restoration of T, B and NK cells in these mice reduced A β pathology and increased microglial activation. These data may suggest a role for non-T and B cells contributing to A β clearance. Further studies crossing *Rag2*^{-/-} mice with APP/PS1 Δ E9 AD mice (now only deficient in B and T cells) showed after bone marrow transfer a significant reduction in A β levels [63]. These studies point to discrepancies in the different models but highlight that AD pathology can be significantly influenced by both T and B cells. Direct antigenic stimulation of either T or B cells was not examined in these studies. It is possible that activation of these cells via this route this could drive an enhanced neuroinflammatory response exacerbating disease progression and thus requires further study.

APP/PS1 AD mouse studies have shown that CD8⁺ T cells can be recruited into the AD brain where they modulate neuronal and synapse related gene expression [59]. However, the authors show that even when APP/PS1-21 AD mice were treated with depleting anti-CD8 antibodies, neither plaque formation or cognition was altered. While not conclusive these findings suggest a role for CD8 in possibly mediating neuroinflammation during AD pathology [59]. When comparing these studies, it is important to consider that the timing of AD onset in the various *in vivo* AD models used can vary. Further direct antigen stimulation, cognitive assessment and A β deposition must also be considered as these can also vary which will dramatically influence the results.

Regulatory T cells (Tregs) have also been implicated in AD development. These CD4⁺ T cells, express the transcription factor Foxp3 and typically regulate the immune system through the production of inhibitory cytokines including TGF- β and IL-10 [64]. An increase in peripheral Foxp3 Tregs has been shown in 5xFAD AD mice and are also systemically elevated in elderly AD patients [65]. Here, mild cognitive impairment (MCI) patients were shown to have increased expression of programmed cell death protein 1 (PD-1)-negative Treg cells. Whilst highly immunosuppressive, this may highlight that excessive immunosuppression may contribute to AD pathology [65]. Baruch *et al* suggested that due to the significant upregulation of Tregs then it would be appropriate to enhance the hosts immune system. Based on this strategy, 5xFAD and APP/PS1-21 AD mice treated with anti-PD-1 monoclonal antibodies showed overall decreased A β plaque formation with a rescue of cognitive performance and promoted monocyte recruitment into the brain [66]. The increase in recruited monocytes correlated with increased IFN- γ release into the choroid plexus that promotes permissive recruitment of other peripheral immune cells into the brain so this increased presence would need to be monitored for any bystander damage [19, 66].

Depleting Tregs *in vivo* by crossing Foxp3-diphtheria toxin mice (*Dtx*) with 5xFAD AD mice, showed that Treg depleted AD mice displayed improved cognitive behaviour with reduced A β pathology but results an influx of macrophages and T cells into the brain [67]. IL-10 signalling has also been shown to be up-regulated in the brains of AD patients and by depleting IL-10 *in vivo* using *Il-10*^{-/-} mice crossed with APP/PS1-21 AD mice, this reduced cognitive decline and cerebral amyloid accumulation [68]. Another source of IL-10 are T_H2 cells, and whilst these cells also display an immunosuppressive phenotype, adoptive transfer of WT T_H2 cells into APP/PS1-21 AD mice can improve cognitive function and reduce AD pathology [69]. This

highlights the therapeutic potential of targeting IL-10 *in vivo* in AD but suggests the direct impact of the cellular source of upregulated IL-10 needs further study.

T_H1 and T_H17 cells have also been shown to drive AD pathology as reviewed in [18] and have both been found in the parenchyma of APP/PS1-21 AD mice [70]. T cells are known to stimulate a wide range of cytokines that can influence microglia and astrocyte function in AD. These have been well classified in [10] but includes upregulation of typical proinflammatory cytokines such as TNF- α , IL-6, IL-1 β and MCP-1 in AD patients which may promote the increased prevalence of T_H1 and T_H17 cells in AD patients [10].

T_H1 cells are a well classified T cell subset that are a major source of IFN- γ release upon antigen recognition. Secretion of IFN- γ can activate both microglia and astrocytes in APP/PS1-21 AD mice which subsequently increases A β deposition and can accelerate cognitive impairment [70]. However, conflicting studies have shown that adoptive transfer of T_H1 cells that are specific for A β into 5xFAD AD mice leads to an increase in T cell mediated activation of MHCII⁺ microglia that display increased phagocytic activity of A β [71].

The role of T_H17 involvement in AD pathology is less well described. However, T_H17 cells have been shown to actively recruit into the parenchyma of rat AD models. Here they have been shown to induce neuroinflammation and neurodegeneration through the production of IL-17 and IL-22 influencing neuronal function mediated through the Fas/FasL apoptotic pathway [72]. Thus, directly targeting the T cell mediated neuroinflammatory response may represent an innovative approach for the design of novel therapies for AD.

It is also worth considering what role the known genetic risk factors of AD as described above can have on T cell function. Humans that express the APOE4 have an increased levels of T cell activation as compared to those that express APOE2 or APOE3 [73]. However *in vitro* studies suggest that APOE lipoproteins can inhibit T cell activation by limiting inflammatory cytokine release [74, 75]. These results have been confirmed in an induced models of multiple sclerosis - the demyelinating neurodegenerative experimental autoimmune encephalomyelitis (EAE) in *Apoe*^{-/-} mice. *Apoe*^{-/-} mice have increased levels of T_H1 and T_H17 cells in their brains with concurrent increases in proinflammatory cytokine release (IL-17, IFN- γ , TNF- α , IL-12, IL-1 β and IL-6) and that readministering an APOE peptide mimetic into these mice reversed the cytokine release. Together this shows how APOE can modulate T_H1 and T_H17 proinflammatory mediated cytokine responses [76] and is a key regulator of T cell activation.

B cells are responsible for and essential to the production of antibodies in mammalian biology [77]. The role of B cells in AD is not fully understood, however, B cells have been shown to be present in the brain parenchyma of 3xTG and APP/PS1-21 AD mice. It was first thought that the presence of B cells in the brain may produce immunoglobulins that may be specific to and interfere with A β plaque formation [78]. Depleting B cells in AD mice by crossing 3xTG or APP/PS1-21 AD mice with J_HT mice (immunoglobulin deficient) resulted in a lack of immunoglobulin deposition in the brain which subsequently blocked AD pathology. This result was also confirmed using anti-B cell blocking antibodies in 5xFAD AD mice thus reinforcing the importance of B cells contributing to AD pathology [78].

NK cells are another subset of immune cells that plays a role in host defence and bridges the divide between the innate and adaptive immune response [79]. These cells can kill an infected cell directly via production of cytokines or mediate antibody dependent cytotoxicity [79]. The role of NK cells in AD is poorly understood but studies have shown that depletion of NK cells using anti-NK1.1 antibodies dramatically improves the cognitive function of 3xTG AD mice. This was associated with a decrease in microglial proliferative capacity and rescued inflammatory cytokine production implying that NK cells may contribute to AD pathology through cytokine mediated inflammation [80]. It has also been shown that in human AD

patients most systemic NK cells contract, however RNA-seq analysis revealed an expansion of a unique NK cell subset expressing *CX3CR1*, *TBX21*, *MYOM2*, *DUSP1* and *ZFP36L2* that may potentially drive NK mediated AD pathology but requires further study [81].

Gamma delta cells have also been implicated in AD pathology. Using T Cell Receptor (TCR) deep sequencing of both human blood and brain samples from AD patients, TCR diversity and somatic variability of the TCR gamma chain (TRG) identified putative clonotypes that were more specific in both brain and blood of AD patients [82]. Whilst this highlights a biased phenotype may contribute to disease, further studies are needed to elucidate the importance of these findings and whether any dominance of the TRG region or other TCR CDR3 regions can be used as markers of AD pathology [82].

T follicular helper T cells (T_{FH}) are a form of $CD4^+$ T cells that are enriched in germinal centres [83]. T_{FH} cells are the main source of proinflammatory IL-21 production which plays a role in B cell Immunoglobulin class switching of IgM to IgG and sustains production of antibodies by differentiated plasma cells (reviewed in [83]). Systemic increases of IL-21 have also been shown in AD patients and in MCI patients. These patients displayed concurrent increases in $A\beta$ peptide-specific plasma IgM and IgG levels [84]. This is also seen in 5xFAD AD mice as compared to controls suggesting an IL-21 T_{FH} -mediated inflammatory response may be contributing to pathology [85]. IL-21 can also stimulate T_{FH} cells in an autocrine manner which could further exacerbate the presence and contribution of T_{FH} cells in AD. An excess production of IL-21 during an inflammatory response also promotes the stimulation of T_H17 cells to produce IL-17 and thus could suggest that T_{FH} cells are an important immune mediator of excessive inflammation of other immune subsets (T_H17 s) in AD [85, 86].

There are other immune cells not discussed at length here that may potentially contribute to AD pathology, however any links have remained to be described. These include mucosal-associated invariant T (MAIT) cells. Interestingly brain astrocytes and microglia can express functional MR1 molecules that present microbial antigens to MAIT cells [87]. It is known that microglia can also express MHC antigens so taken together this further potentiates that microglial antigen recognition by different T cell phenotypes may contribute to AD pathology but will need further study to dissect any link.

Cytokines, Inflammation and AD

As mentioned throughout, AD pathology is exacerbated by the production of cytokines and chemokines which are released either through the interaction between the systemic innate and adaptive immune system driving neuroinflammation, through the interaction of the immune cells with brain resident cells, or released via the brain resident cells themselves. These proteins can be either proinflammatory or immunosuppressive in their capacity to promote typical homeostasis but are dysregulated in AD pathology and their individual influence on disease development have been nicely described previously [10, 88].

The cytokines associated with AD pathology can be produced by microglia, astrocytes, innate and adaptive immune cells. These include those that are most well described that are either pro-inflammatory including IL- $1\beta/\alpha$, IL-6, IL-18, TNF- α , IFN- γ , and those that are anti-inflammatory including IL-4, IL-10 and TGF- β [88]. There are 15 cytokines that have been associated with AD with at least 23 cytokine polymorphisms associated with disease risk [88, 89]. Zheng and colleagues classified all cytokines associated with AD into three main conditions “(1) having polymorphisms that are significantly associated with AD, (2) having corresponding genotype/phenotype data, and (3) having previous records of the changed levels in AD patients” [89]. They went on to sub-classify the cytokines into further groups that possess combinations of these three main conditions [88, 89]. Dysregulation of these

cytokines can then contribute to excessive A β production in an inflammatory manner which subsequently leads to further increases in IL-1 β , IL-6, TNF- α and IFN- γ by glial cells, creating a vicious cycle of pathogenic events [88].

Mononuclear phagocytes such as monocytes and macrophages are one of the primary inducers of inflammation mediated via chemokine release/signalling and have been shown to influence AD pathology as reviewed in [19]. Several chemokines such as CCL2 (MCP-1), CXCL8 (IL-8), CXCL10 (IP-10) and CCL5 (RANTES) are also produced in response to A β peptide deposition. These chemokines can regulate both microglial and astrocyte migration and the recruitment of other peripheral immune cells to promote neuroinflammation [88].

The Interferon (IFN) family have widespread antiviral or immune-modulatory functions. There are three major classes, type-I IFNs comprising IFN- α and IFN- β , type-II IFNs (IFN- γ) and type-III IFNs (IFN- λ) [90]. Cell signalling is induced when type-I IFNs bind to the IFN- $\alpha\beta$ receptor (IFNAR1 and IFNAR2) and initiates transcription of interferon stimulated genes (ISGs) [90]. Multiple studies have shown that ISGs are elevated in the brains of AD patients as compared to healthy controls [91, 92]. This is supported using *in vivo* AD models where type-I IFN activation induces A β pathology in microglia and other neural cells using 5xFAD AD mice [93]. The authors showed that when blocking IFNAR signalling in 5xFAD AD mice reduced microglial cell accumulation and synapse loss [92] and specific deletion of IFNAR1 expressed on microglia rescued memory and synaptic defects [93]. IFNAR1 deletion on other neural cells restored synaptic terminals and decreased A β plaque formation [93]. The importance of type-I IFN signalling in AD pathology was shown in studies using APP/PS1-21 AD mice where primary microglia isolated from the brains of mice with ablated type-I IFN signalling increased the phagocytic capacity to uptake A β 1-42 [94]. As discussed by Sandford *et al* [95], type-I IFN induced immune activation and thus suppression of type-I IFN retains a complex *modus operandi* and it's still not fully understood how IFN production directs the immune system to exacerbate AD pathology and tauopathy [95, 96].

Transcriptomic approaches have revealed a plethora of polymorphisms in ISGs that may increase overall AD risk and requires further study to elucidate more fully the mechanisms underpinning the involvement of these polymorphisms. This is now of significant importance given that the ISG, Interferon Induced Transmembrane protein 3 (IFITM3), a key anti-viral restriction factor, is activated by inflammatory cytokines in neurons and astrocytes and binds gamma-secretase subsequently upregulating A β production. The authors showed that IFITM3 is upregulated in LOAD patients and that crossing *Ifitm3*^{-/-} mice with 5xFAD AD mice resulted in reduced gamma secretase activity with reduced amyloid plaque formation [97]. This supports a role for IFN-induced risk of neuroinflammation and exacerbation of AD pathology.

Infection and AD

Recent data now highlights the potential role of viral-infections in exacerbating cognitive decline and AD. It is well known that many viruses can access the brain driving neurological impairment including Herpes Simplex Virus-1 (HSV-1), SARS-CoV2, Polio and West Nile Virus [98-100]. Further evidence suggests that human herpesviruses (HHV), which establish life-long chronic infections, can be found in the brain of deceased AD patients including HSV-1, HHV-6A and HHV-7 [98, 101] and that infection with the common β -Herpesvirus Human Cytomegalovirus (HCMV) can exacerbate AD with increased localized inflammation found in the blood and brain of AD patients that associate with worsening rates of cognitive decline and an increase accumulation of A β [102-104]. However, there are conflicting epidemiological studies that suggest CMV seroprevalence doesn't associate with AD pathology but co-infection of CMV and HSV-1 does associate with AD development [105]. This co-infection hypothesis is further supported by a recent study showing that HSV-1 and SARS-CoV-2

infection in human CSF can result in amyloid aggregation of proteins known to be involved in AD, including APOE [106]. This may suggest that an active site-specific viral replication within the CNS may be enough to trigger AD pathology.

However, it is also possible that the host's systemic anti-viral inflammatory response may stimulate the immune system to elicit cytokine-mediated neuroinflammation that contributes to AD pathology. Whilst many viral infections have been associated with neurodegenerative disorders, there remains a lack of clear data regarding the viral-induced mechanisms that directly drive AD development and thus requires further study.

Another strong inducer of the immune system includes Sepsis. It has been shown that animal models of Lipopolysaccharide (LPS)-induced bacterial sepsis can result in the increase of proinflammatory cytokines in the brain [107, 108]. Further studies using APP/PS1-21 AD mice showed that polymicrobial activation increased fibrillar A β plaque formation in the hippocampus with increases in astrocyte activation mediated by C4b gene expression, thus increasing brain-specific inflammation [107]. *Porphyromonas gingivalis* infection, the main cause of chronic periodontitis, can also induce neuroinflammation and has been associated with an increased risk of developing AD with elevated A β 1-42 levels shown in *ApoE*^{-/-} mice [109]. Similarly to viral-infections, strong inducers of the immune system such as sepsis may contribute and exacerbate AD pathology and requires further study.

Immunotherapy

There have been many studies that have taken an immunotherapeutic approach that specifically targets A β to prevent plaque formation for effective treatment of AD [110]. These approaches used either synthetic A β peptides (AN1792) to stimulate anti A β antibodies [111, 112], or use antibodies to target various regions of A β [110]. However, these studies have failed due to lack of efficacy and safety concerns. Further direct entry of antibodies into the brain poses a clinical challenge as well as the timings required to treat an individual recruited into a trial who may already have different levels of A β throughout the cohort [19].

There have been more recent proof of concept approaches targeting A β using anti-IgG1 antibody therapy (Gantenerumab and Lecanemab) which have been designated 'Breakthrough Therapies' by the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) [113, 114]. Both antibodies, in Phase II and Phase III trials respectively, using between 850 and 2000 patients, showed reduction of A β plaques and slowed cognitive decline. Lecanemab is intended for early-stage AD and resulted in a 27% reduction in cognitive decline with reduced plasma A β 42/40 ratio and reduced amyloid in the brain [115]. The findings of both drugs await the results of larger Phase III trials as Gantenerumab has failed to yet reach its key secondary endpoints. The only approved monoclonal antibody therapy that targets A β is Aducanumab that leads to a reduction in amyloid however the approval of this drug are still debated [116-118].

Based on the mostly failed approaches and more recently the mild benefits of 'breakthrough' drugs that target A β , it is therefore appropriate to also target the immune system for effective AD treatment utilising the approaches that target various immune pathways as described throughout. The success and efficacy of studies that use immune system-specific therapeutic approaches suggests that it may be useful to design studies that target both A β with immune modulator/s to maximise any potential success of an immunotherapeutic approach for AD.

Closing remarks

AD represents one of the greatest burdens to global public health as humans age and live longer. Without any effective therapies to appropriately treat the disease with strong efficacy, the patient and economic burdens will become overwhelming. The studies that have been discussed here highlights the link between immune system-mediated inflammation with AD pathology and neurodegeneration. While therapeutic studies have mostly focused on targeting A β this has resulted in an effective treatment remaining elusive. Identifying the specific roles that the immune system plays in neuroinflammation throughout the course of AD pathology is therefore critical. Identifying the key interplay between both the innate and adaptive immune response, including the immune-mediated inflammatory responses, with brain resident cells will promote more understanding into the role of the immune system in AD. Whether this is due to an innate or adaptive anti-pathogen response driving neuroinflammation in conjunction with genetic risk factors of disease requires further study, but the data discussed here highlights the significant contribution the immune system plays in AD pathology. Together, identifying new prognostic markers of disease, related to and derived from the immune system, will be crucial in developing novel therapies which will alleviate the symptoms of this debilitating disease and prevent neurodegeneration in AD.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

References

1. Mrdjen, D., et al., *High-Dimensional Single-Cell Mapping of Central Nervous System Immune Cells Reveals Distinct Myeloid Subsets in Health, Aging, and Disease*. *Immunity*, 2018. **48**(2): p. 380-395 e6.
2. Office for National Statistics. *Deaths*. Available from: <https://www.ons.gov.uk/peoplepopulationandcommunity/birthsdeathsandmarriages/deaths>.
3. Alzheimer's Society. *Dementia UK report*. Available from: <https://www.alzheimers.org.uk/about-us/policy-and-influencing/dementia-uk-report>.
4. Bloom, G.S., *Amyloid-beta and tau: the trigger and bullet in Alzheimer disease pathogenesis*. *JAMA Neurol*, 2014. **71**(4): p. 505-8.
5. Canter, R.G., J. Penney, and L.H. Tsai, *The road to restoring neural circuits for the treatment of Alzheimer's disease*. *Nature*, 2016. **539**(7628): p. 187-196.
6. Trambauer, J., et al., *Analyzing Amyloid-beta Peptide Modulation Profiles and Binding Sites of gamma-Secretase Modulators*. *Enzymology at the Membrane Interface: Intramembrane Proteases*, 2017. **584**: p. 157-183.
7. Murphy, M.P. and H. LeVine, *Alzheimer's Disease and the Amyloid-beta Peptide*. *Journal of Alzheimers Disease*, 2010. **19**(1): p. 311-323.
8. Chen, X. and D.M. Holtzman, *Emerging roles of innate and adaptive immunity in Alzheimer's disease*. *Immunity*, 2022. **55**(12): p. 2236-2254.
9. Rubin, L., et al., *Genetic Risk Factors for Alzheimer's Disease in Racial/Ethnic Minority Populations in the U.S.: A Scoping Review*. *Front Public Health*, 2021. **9**: p. 784958.
10. Frost, G.R., L.A. Jonas, and Y.M. Li, *Friend, Foe or Both? Immune Activity in Alzheimer's Disease*. *Front Aging Neurosci*, 2019. **11**: p. 337.
11. Muzio, L., A. Viotti, and G. Martino, *Microglia in Neuroinflammation and Neurodegeneration: From Understanding to Therapy*. *Frontiers in Neuroscience*, 2021. **15**.
12. Corder, E.H., et al., *Gene Dose of Apolipoprotein-E Type-4 Allele and the Risk of Alzheimers-Disease in Late-Onset Families*. *Science*, 1993. **261**(5123): p. 921-923.
13. Morris, J.C., et al., *APOE predicts amyloid-beta but not tau Alzheimer pathology in cognitively normal aging*. *Ann Neurol*, 2010. **67**(1): p. 122-31.
14. Vergheze, P.B., et al., *ApoE influences amyloid-beta (Abeta) clearance despite minimal apoE/Abeta association in physiological conditions*. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*, 2013. **110**(19): p. E1807-16.
15. Shi, Y., et al., *ApoE4 markedly exacerbates tau-mediated neurodegeneration in a mouse model of tauopathy*. *Nature*, 2017. **549**(7673): p. 523-527.
16. Yoshiyama, Y., et al., *Synapse loss and microglial activation precede tangles in a P301S tauopathy mouse model*. *Neuron*, 2007. **53**(3): p. 337-51.
17. Montagne, A., et al., *APOE4 leads to blood-brain barrier dysfunction predicting cognitive decline*. *Nature*, 2020. **581**(7806): p. 71-76.
18. Dai, L. and Y. Shen, *Insights into T-cell dysfunction in Alzheimer's disease*. *Aging Cell*, 2021. **20**(12): p. e13511.
19. Jevtic, S., et al., *The role of the immune system in Alzheimer disease: Etiology and treatment*. *Ageing Res Rev*, 2017. **40**: p. 84-94.
20. Shi, Y. and D.M. Holtzman, *Interplay between innate immunity and Alzheimer disease: APOE and TREM2 in the spotlight*. *Nat Rev Immunol*, 2018. **18**(12): p. 759-772.
21. Atagi, Y., et al., *Apolipoprotein E Is a Ligand for Triggering Receptor Expressed on Myeloid Cells 2 (TREM2)*. *J Biol Chem*, 2015. **290**(43): p. 26043-50.
22. Suarez-Calvet, M., et al., *Early changes in CSF sTREM2 in dominantly inherited Alzheimer's disease occur after amyloid deposition and neuronal injury*. *Sci Transl Med*, 2016. **8**(369): p. 369ra178.
23. Suarez-Calvet, M., et al., *Early increase of CSF sTREM2 in Alzheimer's disease is associated with tau related-neurodegeneration but not with amyloid-beta pathology*. *Mol Neurodegener*, 2019. **14**(1): p. 1.

24. Takahashi, K., et al., *TREM2-transduced myeloid precursors mediate nervous tissue debris clearance and facilitate recovery in an animal model of multiple sclerosis*. PLoS Med, 2007. **4**(4): p. e124.
25. Neumann, H., M.R. Kotter, and R.J. Franklin, *Debris clearance by microglia: an essential link between degeneration and regeneration*. Brain, 2009. **132**(Pt 2): p. 288-95.
26. Neumann, H. and K. Takahashi, *Essential role of the microglial triggering receptor expressed on myeloid cells-2 (TREM2) for central nervous tissue immune homeostasis*. J Neuroimmunol, 2007. **184**(1-2): p. 92-9.
27. Cheng-Hathaway, P.J., et al., *The Trem2 R47H variant confers loss-of-function-like phenotypes in Alzheimer's disease*. Mol Neurodegener, 2018. **13**(1): p. 29.
28. Jiang, T., et al., *TREM2 modifies microglial phenotype and provides neuroprotection in P301S tau transgenic mice*. Neuropharmacology, 2016. **105**: p. 196-206.
29. Jonsson, T., et al., *Variant of TREM2 associated with the risk of Alzheimer's disease*. N Engl J Med, 2013. **368**(2): p. 107-16.
30. Fassler, M., et al., *Engagement of TREM2 by a novel monoclonal antibody induces activation of microglia and improves cognitive function in Alzheimer's disease models*. J Neuroinflammation, 2021. **18**(1): p. 19.
31. Wang, S., et al., *Anti-human TREM2 induces microglia proliferation and reduces pathology in an Alzheimer's disease model*. J Exp Med, 2020. **217**(9).
32. van Lengerich, B., et al., *A TREM2-activating antibody with a blood-brain barrier transport vehicle enhances microglial metabolism in Alzheimer's disease models*. Nat Neurosci, 2023.
33. Chan, G., et al., *CD33 modulates TREM2: convergence of Alzheimer loci*. Nat Neurosci, 2015. **18**(11): p. 1556-8.
34. Gu, X., et al., *Peripheral level of CD33 and Alzheimer's disease: a bidirectional two-sample Mendelian randomization study*. Transl Psychiatry, 2022. **12**(1): p. 427.
35. Wissfeld, J., et al., *Deletion of Alzheimer's disease-associated CD33 results in an inflammatory human microglia phenotype*. Glia, 2021. **69**(6): p. 1393-1412.
36. Da Mesquita, S., et al., *Functional aspects of meningeal lymphatics in ageing and Alzheimer's disease*. Nature, 2018. **560**(7717): p. 185-191.
37. Herisson, F., et al., *Direct vascular channels connect skull bone marrow and the brain surface enabling myeloid cell migration*. Nat Neurosci, 2018. **21**(9): p. 1209-1217.
38. Shaked, I., et al., *Early activation of microglia as antigen-presenting cells correlates with T cell-mediated protection and repair of the injured central nervous system*. J Neuroimmunol, 2004. **146**(1-2): p. 84-93.
39. Torvell, M., et al., *Genetic Insights into the Impact of Complement in Alzheimer's Disease*. Genes (Basel), 2021. **12**(12).
40. Morgan, B.P., *Complement in the pathogenesis of Alzheimer's disease*. Semin Immunopathol, 2018. **40**(1): p. 113-124.
41. Rogers, J., et al., *Complement activation by beta-amyloid in Alzheimer disease*. Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A, 1992. **89**(21): p. 10016-20.
42. Yin, C., et al., *ApoE attenuates unresolvable inflammation by complex formation with activated C1q*. Nat Med, 2019. **25**(3): p. 496-506.
43. Lian, H., et al., *NFkappaB-activated astroglial release of complement C3 compromises neuronal morphology and function associated with Alzheimer's disease*. Neuron, 2015. **85**(1): p. 101-115.
44. Lian, H., et al., *Astrocyte-Microglia Cross Talk through Complement Activation Modulates Amyloid Pathology in Mouse Models of Alzheimer's Disease*. J Neurosci, 2016. **36**(2): p. 577-89.
45. Litvinchuk, A., et al., *Complement C3aR Inactivation Attenuates Tau Pathology and Reverses an Immune Network Deregulated in Tauopathy Models and Alzheimer's Disease*. Neuron, 2018. **100**(6): p. 1337-1353 e5.
46. Shi, Q., et al., *Complement C3 deficiency protects against neurodegeneration in aged plaque-rich APP/PS1 mice*. Sci Transl Med, 2017. **9**(392).

47. Ascolani, A., et al., *Dysregulated NF-kappaB pathway in peripheral mononuclear cells of Alzheimer's disease patients*. *Curr Alzheimer Res*, 2012. **9**(1): p. 128-37.
48. Kitamura, Y., et al., *Alteration of transcription factors NF-kappaB and STAT1 in Alzheimer's disease brains*. *Neurosci Lett*, 1997. **237**(1): p. 17-20.
49. Krstic, D., et al., *Systemic immune challenges trigger and drive Alzheimer-like neuropathology in mice*. *J Neuroinflammation*, 2012. **9**: p. 151.
50. Liu, T., et al., *NF-kappaB signaling in inflammation*. *Signal Transduct Target Ther*, 2017. **2**: p. 17023-.
51. Bai, H. and Q. Zhang, *Activation of NLRP3 Inflammasome and Onset of Alzheimer's Disease*. *Front Immunol*, 2021. **12**: p. 701282.
52. Heneka, M.T., et al., *NLRP3 is activated in Alzheimer's disease and contributes to pathology in APP/PS1 mice*. *Nature*, 2013. **493**(7434): p. 674-8.
53. Zenaro, E., et al., *Neutrophils promote Alzheimer's disease-like pathology and cognitive decline via LFA-1 integrin*. *Nat Med*, 2015. **21**(8): p. 880-6.
54. Baik, S.H., et al., *Migration of neutrophils targeting amyloid plaques in Alzheimer's disease mouse model*. *Neurobiol Aging*, 2014. **35**(6): p. 1286-92.
55. Moir, R.D., R. Lathe, and R.E. Tanzi, *The antimicrobial protection hypothesis of Alzheimer's disease*. *Alzheimers Dement*, 2018. **14**(12): p. 1602-1614.
56. Soscia, S.J., et al., *The Alzheimer's disease-associated amyloid beta-protein is an antimicrobial peptide*. *PLoS One*, 2010. **5**(3): p. e9505.
57. Kumar, D.K., et al., *Amyloid-beta peptide protects against microbial infection in mouse and worm models of Alzheimer's disease*. *Sci Transl Med*, 2016. **8**(340): p. 340ra72.
58. Eimer, W.A., et al., *Alzheimer's Disease-Associated beta-Amyloid Is Rapidly Seeded by Herpesviridae to Protect against Brain Infection*. *Neuron*, 2018. **99**(1): p. 56-63 e3.
59. Unger, M.S., et al., *CD8(+) T-cells infiltrate Alzheimer's disease brains and regulate neuronal- and synapse-related gene expression in APP-PS1 transgenic mice*. *Brain Behav Immun*, 2020. **89**: p. 67-86.
60. Merlini, M., et al., *Extravascular CD3+ T Cells in Brains of Alzheimer Disease Patients Correlate with Tau but Not with Amyloid Pathology: An Immunohistochemical Study*. *Neurodegener Dis*, 2018. **18**(1): p. 49-56.
61. Franceschi, C., et al., *Inflamm-aging. An evolutionary perspective on immunosenescence*. *Ann N Y Acad Sci*, 2000. **908**: p. 244-54.
62. Marsh, S.E., et al., *The adaptive immune system restrains Alzheimer's disease pathogenesis by modulating microglial function*. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*, 2016. **113**(9): p. E1316-25.
63. Spani, C., et al., *Reduced beta-amyloid pathology in an APP transgenic mouse model of Alzheimer's disease lacking functional B and T cells*. *Acta Neuropathol Commun*, 2015. **3**: p. 71.
64. Zhao, H., X. Liao, and Y. Kang, *Tregs: Where We Are and What Comes Next?* *Front Immunol*, 2017. **8**: p. 1578.
65. Saresella, M., et al., *PD1 negative and PD1 positive CD4+ T regulatory cells in mild cognitive impairment and Alzheimer's disease*. *J Alzheimers Dis*, 2010. **21**(3): p. 927-38.
66. Baruch, K., et al., *PD-1 immune checkpoint blockade reduces pathology and improves memory in mouse models of Alzheimer's disease*. *Nat Med*, 2016. **22**(2): p. 135-7.
67. Baruch, K., et al., *Breaking immune tolerance by targeting Foxp3(+) regulatory T cells mitigates Alzheimer's disease pathology*. *Nat Commun*, 2015. **6**: p. 7967.
68. Guillot-Sestier, M.V., et al., *Il10 deficiency rebalances innate immunity to mitigate Alzheimer-like pathology*. *Neuron*, 2015. **85**(3): p. 534-48.
69. Cao, C., et al., *Abeta-specific Th2 cells provide cognitive and pathological benefits to Alzheimer's mice without infiltrating the CNS*. *Neurobiol Dis*, 2009. **34**(1): p. 63-70.
70. Browne, T.C., et al., *IFN-gamma Production by amyloid beta-specific Th1 cells promotes microglial activation and increases plaque burden in a mouse model of Alzheimer's disease*. *J Immunol*, 2013. **190**(5): p. 2241-51.

71. Mittal, K., et al., *CD4 T Cells Induce A Subset of MHCII-Expressing Microglia that Attenuates Alzheimer Pathology*. *iScience*, 2019. **16**: p. 298-311.
72. Zhang, J., et al., *Th17 cell-mediated neuroinflammation is involved in neurodegeneration of abeta1-42-induced Alzheimer's disease model rats*. *PLoS One*, 2013. **8**(10): p. e75786.
73. Bonacina, F., et al., *Myeloid apolipoprotein E controls dendritic cell antigen presentation and T cell activation*. *Nat Commun*, 2018. **9**(1): p. 3083.
74. Kelly, M.E., et al., *Apolipoprotein E inhibition of proliferation of mitogen-activated T lymphocytes: production of interleukin 2 with reduced biological activity*. *Cell Immunol*, 1994. **159**(2): p. 124-39.
75. Macy, M., et al., *Suppression of lymphocyte activation by plasma lipoproteins*. *Cancer Res*, 1983. **43**(5 Suppl): p. 2496s-2502s.
76. Wei, J., et al., *Apolipoprotein E and its mimetic peptide suppress Th1 and Th17 responses in experimental autoimmune encephalomyelitis*. *Neurobiol Dis*, 2013. **56**: p. 59-65.
77. Somers, V., et al., *Editorial: New Insights Into B Cell Subsets in Health and Disease*. *Front Immunol*, 2022. **13**: p. 854889.
78. Kim, K., et al., *Therapeutic B-cell depletion reverses progression of Alzheimer's disease*. *Nat Commun*, 2021. **12**(1): p. 2185.
79. Pierce, S., E.S. Geanes, and T. Bradley, *Targeting Natural Killer Cells for Improved Immunity and Control of the Adaptive Immune Response*. *Front Cell Infect Microbiol*, 2020. **10**: p. 231.
80. Zhang, Y., et al., *Depletion of NK Cells Improves Cognitive Function in the Alzheimer Disease Mouse Model*. *J Immunol*, 2020. **205**(2): p. 502-510.
81. Qi, C., et al., *Alzheimer's disease alters the transcriptomic profile of natural killer cells at single-cell resolution*. *Front Immunol*, 2022. **13**: p. 1004885.
82. Aliseychik, M., et al., *Dissection of the Human T-Cell Receptor gamma Gene Repertoire in the Brain and Peripheral Blood Identifies Age- and Alzheimer's Disease-Associated Clonotype Profiles*. *Front Immunol*, 2020. **11**: p. 12.
83. Krishnaswamy, J.K., et al., *Determination of T Follicular Helper Cell Fate by Dendritic Cells*. *Front Immunol*, 2018. **9**: p. 2169.
84. Agrawal, S., et al., *IgM response against amyloid-beta in aging: a potential peripheral protective mechanism*. *Alzheimers Res Ther*, 2018. **10**(1): p. 81.
85. Baulch, J.E., et al., *Immune and Inflammatory Determinants Underlying Alzheimer's Disease Pathology*. *J Neuroimmune Pharmacol*, 2020. **15**(4): p. 852-862.
86. Spolski, R. and W.J. Leonard, *Interleukin-21: a double-edged sword with therapeutic potential*. *Nat Rev Drug Discov*, 2014. **13**(5): p. 379-95.
87. Priya, R. and R.R. Brutkiewicz, *Brain astrocytes and microglia express functional MR1 molecules that present microbial antigens to mucosal-associated invariant T (MAIT) cells*. *J Neuroimmunol*, 2020. **349**: p. 577428.
88. Domingues, C., E.S.O.A.B. da Cruz, and A.G. Henriques, *Impact of Cytokines and Chemokines on Alzheimer's Disease Neuropathological Hallmarks*. *Curr Alzheimer Res*, 2017. **14**(8): p. 870-882.
89. Zheng, C., X.W. Zhou, and J.Z. Wang, *The dual roles of cytokines in Alzheimer's disease: update on interleukins, TNF-alpha, TGF-beta and IFN-gamma*. *Transl Neurodegener*, 2016. **5**: p. 7.
90. McNab, F., et al., *Type I interferons in infectious disease*. *Nat Rev Immunol*, 2015. **15**(2): p. 87-103.
91. Taylor, J.M., et al., *Type-1 interferon signaling mediates neuro-inflammatory events in models of Alzheimer's disease*. *Neurobiol Aging*, 2014. **35**(5): p. 1012-23.
92. Roy, E.R., et al., *Type I interferon response drives neuroinflammation and synapse loss in Alzheimer disease*. *J Clin Invest*, 2020. **130**(4): p. 1912-1930.
93. Roy, E.R., et al., *Concerted type I interferon signaling in microglia and neural cells promotes memory impairment associated with amyloid beta plaques*. *Immunity*, 2022. **55**(5): p. 879-894 e6.

94. Moore, Z., et al., *Abrogation of type-I interferon signalling alters the microglial response to Aβ(1-42)*. *Sci Rep*, 2020. **10**(1): p. 3153.
95. Sanford, S.A.I. and W.A. McEwan, *Type-I Interferons in Alzheimer's Disease and Other Tauopathies*. *Front Cell Neurosci*, 2022. **16**: p. 949340.
96. Salih, D.A., et al., *Genetic variability in response to amyloid beta deposition influences Alzheimer's disease risk*. *Brain Commun*, 2019. **1**(1): p. fcz022.
97. Hur, J.Y., et al., *The innate immunity protein IFITM3 modulates gamma-secretase in Alzheimer's disease*. *Nature*, 2020. **586**(7831): p. 735-740.
98. Itzhaki, R.F., *Overwhelming Evidence for a Major Role for Herpes Simplex Virus Type 1 (HSV1) in Alzheimer's Disease (AD); Underwhelming Evidence against. Vaccines (Basel)*, 2021. **9**(6).
99. Steardo, L., et al., *Neuroinfection may contribute to pathophysiology and clinical manifestations of COVID-19*. *Acta Physiol (Oxf)*, 2020. **229**(3): p. e13473.
100. van den Pol, A.N., *Viral infections in the developing and mature brain*. *Trends Neurosci*, 2006. **29**(7): p. 398-406.
101. Readhead, B., et al., *Multiscale Analysis of Independent Alzheimer's Cohorts Finds Disruption of Molecular, Genetic, and Clinical Networks by Human Herpesvirus*. *Neuron*, 2018. **99**(1): p. 64-82 e7.
102. Barnes, L.L., et al., *Cytomegalovirus infection and risk of Alzheimer disease in older black and white individuals*. *J Infect Dis*, 2015. **211**(2): p. 230-7.
103. Westman, G., et al., *Increased inflammatory response in cytomegalovirus seropositive patients with Alzheimer's disease*. *PLoS One*, 2014. **9**(5): p. e96779.
104. Lurain, N.S., et al., *Virological and immunological characteristics of human cytomegalovirus infection associated with Alzheimer disease*. *J Infect Dis*, 2013. **208**(4): p. 564-72.
105. Lovheim, H., et al., *Interaction between Cytomegalovirus and Herpes Simplex Virus Type 1 Associated with the Risk of Alzheimer's Disease Development*. *J Alzheimers Dis*, 2018. **61**(3): p. 939-945.
106. Christ, W., et al., *SARS-CoV-2 and HSV-1 Induce Amyloid Aggregation in Human CSF*. *bioRxiv*, 2022: p. 2022.09.15.508120.
107. Basak, J.M., et al., *Bacterial sepsis increases hippocampal fibrillar amyloid plaque load and neuroinflammation in a mouse model of Alzheimer's disease*. *Neurobiology of Disease*, 2021. **152**.
108. Zhao, J., et al., *Neuroinflammation induced by lipopolysaccharide causes cognitive impairment in mice*. *Sci Rep*, 2019. **9**(1): p. 5790.
109. Dominy, S.S., et al., *Porphyromonas gingivalis in Alzheimer's disease brains: Evidence for disease causation and treatment with small-molecule inhibitors*. *Sci Adv*, 2019. **5**(1): p. eaau3333.
110. Song, C., et al., *Immunotherapy for Alzheimer's disease: targeting beta-amyloid and beyond*. *Transl Neurodegener*, 2022. **11**(1): p. 18.
111. Gilman, S., et al., *Clinical effects of Aβ immunization (AN1792) in patients with AD in an interrupted trial*. *Neurology*, 2005. **64**(9): p. 1553-62.
112. Cao, J., et al., *Advances in developing novel therapeutic strategies for Alzheimer's disease*. *Mol Neurodegener*, 2018. **13**(1): p. 64.
113. Decourt, B., et al., *Critical Appraisal of Amyloid Lowering Agents in AD*. *Curr Neurol Neurosci Rep*, 2021. **21**(8): p. 39.
114. Genentech. *Genentech's Anti-Amyloid Beta Antibody Gantenerumab Granted FDA Breakthrough Therapy Designation in Alzheimer's Disease*. 2021 [cited 2021 08/10/2021]; Available from: <https://www.gene.com/media/press-releases/14931/2021-10-08/genentechs-anti-amyloid-beta-antibody-ga>.
115. van Dyck, C.H., et al., *Lecanemab in Early Alzheimer's Disease*. *N Engl J Med*, 2023. **388**(1): p. 9-21.
116. Bateman, R.J., et al., *Gantenerumab: an anti-amyloid monoclonal antibody with potential disease-modifying effects in early Alzheimer's disease*. *Alzheimers Res Ther*, 2022. **14**(1): p. 178.

117. Food, U. and D. Administration, *FDA grants accelerated approval for Alzheimer's drug*. FDA News Release, 2021.
118. Lancet, T., *Lecanemab for Alzheimer's disease: tempering hype and hope*. Lancet, 2022. **400**(10367): p. 1899.